

Green composites from Woven Flax Fiber and Bio-copolyester

BR Guduri ^{a*}, H Semosa ^a and Y. Z. Meng ^b

^aPolymers and Biomaterials, Materials Science & Manufacturing, CSIR
P.O.Box: 395, Pretoria 0001. South Africa.
E-mail: bguduri@csir.co.za

^bInstitute of Environment Materials, Sun Yat-Sen University, Guangzhou
510275, P. R. China.
E-mail: mengyzh@mail.sysu.edu.cn

SUMMARY

In this work, natural fiber based green composites were prepared using natural fiber of flax woven fabric and aliphatic-aromatic copolyester matrix. The composites were prepared by compression moulding using a film stacking method. The mechanical, DMA and morphological properties of the green composites were investigated. The woven flax fibers were treated with different concentrations of NaOH at room temperature for 1 hour. Untreated and NaOH treated fiber surfaces were analysed using FT-IR and SEM. The thermal stability of the untreated and alkali treated woven flax fibers were studied using the thermogravimetric analyser (TGA). The result proves that appropriate alkali treatment is a key technology for improving mechanical properties of cellulose-based fiber composites.

Key words : green composites; woven flax fiber; alkali treatment; FT-IR; DMA; SEM; mechanical properties; TGA.

1. INTRODUCTIN

The use of traditional composites made by glass, aramid or carbon fiber reinforced plastics has recently been discussed critically because of increasing environmental consciousness [1]. Thus, the recent research and development efforts have led to new products based on natural resources. Some of these are biodegradable polymers like PLA (polylactic acid), cellulose esters, polyhydroxyalkanotes and starch polymers. Furthermore, natural fibre-reinforced plastics made with natural fibres like flax, hemp, kenaf, jute and cotton fibres are important research and development (R&D) achievements. Composites made by natural fibers and biopolymers are completely biodegradable and are called “green composites” because of their environmentally beneficial properties [2]. The lower price in manufacturing as well as the better performance of traditional, petrochemical plastics compared to polymers based on natural resources are the outcomes of the R&D efforts of several decades, whereas only

recently scientists have been trying to improve biopolymers so that they can become cheaper and more competitive [1]. Natural fibers as reinforcement for petrochemical polymers like PP (polypropylene) have already been established in the automotive industry [3]. Natural fibers themselves are fiber-reinforced structures in which the cellulose content and the angle of microfibrils influence their mechanical properties [4].

Natural fibers are light and renewable; they are a low-cost and high specific strength resource. For those reasons, natural fiber composites have already been applied for fabricating some products such as furniture and architectural components. Recently, they have gained widespread use in the automobile industry. In their application synthetic resins, such as polypropylene and polyethylene, are commonly used as a matrix for natural fiber composites. However, those composites often display problems of fiber-matrix compatibility which results in a decrease of mechanical properties. Therefore, in order to improve the interaction between fiber and matrix, surface treatments are necessary for modifying the fiber morphology. Treatments using alkaline solutions have been applied by several researches [5-8] to improve mechanical properties and fiber-matrix adhesion of natural fiber reinforced plastics. The fiber undergoes physical changes as a result of bleaching during alkali treatment, which removes waxy materials and impurities. This action often leads to improvement of the interfacial bonding between fiber and matrix.

The main obstacles in the use of natural fibers in plastics have been the poor compatibility between the fibers and the matrix, and the inherent high moisture absorption, which could result in dimensional changes of the fibers that may lead to microcracking of the composite and poor mechanical properties. Various chemical treatments have been used by many researchers in the past to improve the mechanical performance of natural fibers, including jute and hemp [11-13].

Not much literature on the adhesion between the matrix and the fibers in “green composites” have been published, although it influences their mechanical properties significantly. Most of the publications are based on the interaction between fibers and polyolefins. It is known that natural fibers have poor adhesion to hydrophobic matrices like PP because of their hydrophobic nature [14]. Heinemann and Fritx observed a better interaction between PLA and natural fibers than between PP and natural fibers [15]. Oksman et al [16] reported on long fiber pull-outs and clean fiber surfaces in the fracture surface of the PLA/flax fiber composites, which indicates poor adhesion between the fibers and the matrix. Our main research work focuses on the development of completely biodegradable composites by using natural fibers of woven flax as a reinforcement and a co-biopolyester as a matrix material.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Materials

Ecoflex[®] (aliphatic and aromatic co-polyester) was supplied in form of granules by BASF, South Africa. This biothermoplastic has a density of 1.25-1.27 g/cm³; a melting temperature of 110-120 °C, transparency of 82%, tensile strength of 35/44 N/mm² and fracture energy of 24 J/mm. The NaOH was purchased from Sigma-

Aldrich. Woven flax fiber mat was supplied by the Fibers & Textiles centre of the CSIR, which is located in Port Elizabeth, South Africa.

2.2. Alkali Treatment

Woven flax fiber mats were cut into 30x30 cm pieces and immersed in 4, 6, and 8% of NaOH solution at room temperature for 1 hour. The fiber mats were removed from the alkali solution and were then washed several times with fresh water to remove any NaOH sticking to the fiber surface, neutralized with dilute acetic acid, and finally washed again with distilled water. A final pH of 7 was maintained. The fiber mats were then dried at room temperature for 48 h followed by oven drying at 70 °C overnight.

2.3. Composite manufacture

The untreated and NaOH treated woven flax mats were dried in an air circulated oven at 70 °C for 24 hours to remove the moisture before processing the composites. A pellet type co-polyester matrix was used as received and was converted into films of 1.5 mm thickness by a compression molder at 140 °C and a pressure of 200 psi for 3 min. Next the pressure was increased to 450 psi at the same temperature for another 3 min followed by cooling under pressure and finally removed when the temperature reached 80 °C. The co-polyester films were collected and stored in the laboratory under ambient conditions prior to use. The composites were prepared by the compression molding method using the film-stacking procedure. Three layers of woven flax fiber mats were placed alternately between five co-polyester films in parallel arrays and the whole assembly was carefully placed in the press with controlled temperature and pressure.

The composites were prepared at 140 °C under constant pressure of 1500 psi for 5 min followed by cooling under pressure. When the mold temperature reached 80 °C, the plates were opened and the composite was removed from the press. All of the composites contained 60% fibre loading and different percentages of NaOH treatments. The composite samples were cut to the desired shapes for mechanical and dynamic mechanical evaluation.

2.4. Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA)

The storage modulus and tan delta of the untreated and NaOH treated woven composite specimens were measured as a function of temperature from -75 °C to 150 °C using a Perkin Elmer Diamond DMA with a dual cantilever in the bending mode. The experiments were done at a frequency of 1 Hz. The sample dimensions were 50 mm × 10 mm × 2 mm.

2.5. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

The surface and fracture morphology of the untreated and NaOH treated woven flax fiber and composites were observed by using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) at room temperature. A JEOL (model JSM 6300) SEM with field emission gun and accelerating voltage of 5 kV was used to collect SEM pictures of the fiber and composites. The fiber surface and fracture surface was coated with gold and then

samples were viewed parallel for fiber surface and perpendicular to the fracture surfaces of the composites.

2.6. Mechanical properties

The tensile and flexural properties were characterised by using a UTM (Universal Testing Machine) according to ASTM D 630 and D 790 standards. The test speed for both (tensile and flexural) was 5 mm/min. Seven samples were used for each test and the average value was taken.

2.7. FT-IR analysis

The chemical components of untreated and alkali treated woven flax fiber was studied by using a Perkin Elmer FT-IR spectrophotometer. Each spectrum was obtained by adding 64 consecutive scans with a resolution 4 cm^{-1} within the range of $600\text{-}4000\text{cm}^{-1}$.

2.8. TGA analysis

Untreated and alkali treated woven flax fibers were subjected to thermogravimetric analysis by using a Perkin-Elmer Pyris-7, USA equipment. Samples of $\leq 10\text{ mg}$ weight were scanned from $30\text{ to }700\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at a heating rate of $10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ under nitrogen atmosphere and the corresponding weight loss was recorded.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Fiber properties

Fig.1(A) shows the FT-IR spectrum of alkali treated and untreated woven flax fibers. The comparison of the representative FT-IR spectra of untreated and alkali treated fibers are in the same figure (Fig.1 (A)). For untreated and alkali treated woven flax fibers, an intense and broad peak ranging from $3024\text{ to }3691\text{ cm}^{-1}$ was due to the hydrogen bonded -OH vibration of the cellulose structure of flax fiber. The peak at 2917 cm^{-1} has been assigned to the C-H stretching vibration from the -CH_2 group of cellulose and hemicellulose. The peak at 1735 cm^{-1} is attributed to the C-O stretching of the carbonyl groups (>C=O) in hemicellulose. The most notable changes in the FT-IR spectrum of the alkali treated flax fibers are the absence of the characteristic peaks at 1735 cm^{-1} and 1251 cm^{-1} , which are associated with hemicellulose and lignin. For the alkali treated fibers, the intense peak at 1735 cm^{-1} disappeared and this indicates that all the hemicellulose and bonding material was removed on the surface of the treated fibers. These results indicate that the ester group in hemicellulose is more easily removed by an alkali treatment. Mwaikambo and Ansell [17] also reported that the alkali treatment is prone to attack the hemicellulose in sisal and jute rather than lignin. The peak at 1606 cm^{-1} is due to absorbed water [18].

Fig. 1 (B) shows the TGA thermograms of untreated and alkali treated woven flax fibres. It can be seen that the thermal degradation of the alkali treated and untreated flax fibers has taken place within the programmed temperature range of 30-600 °C. After alkali treatment, the temperature at the maximum rate of decomposition of the fiber increased for 4% and 6% treated fibers. This indicates that the alkali solution treatment improved the thermal stability of the flax fiber. This is due to the fact that the relative content of lignin and hemicellulose on the flax fiber surface was removed, as evidenced by FT-IR and SEM analyses (Fig.1 a(A) and 2 (c and d)). Fig. 1 (B) clearly shows that the maximum decomposition rate temperature of the treated fibers (except 8%) was slightly shifted to a higher temperature. However, the thermal stability of the treated flax fiber was dependent on the concentration of the alkali solution and the treatment time.

Figure 1. Treated and untreated woven flax fiber properties; (A) FT-IR spectrum; (B) TGA thermographs

Scanning electron microscopy provides an excellent technique for examining the surface morphology of untreated and treated flax fibers. It is expected that the surface morphology of the untreated fiber will be different to that of the treated fiber, particularly in terms of the fiber surface topography. This could provide vital information on the level of interfacial adhesion that would later exist between the fiber and the matrix when used as a reinforcement with and without treatment. It is well established that the cellulose chains of natural fibers are strongly bound by lignin and hemicellulose, resulting in the formation of multicellular fibers [19]. Fig. 2 (a) shows the SEM micrograph of untreated flax fiber. This picture shows that the surface of the untreated fibers consists of aligned fibrils with material cementing the fibers together. In addition, some impurities were observed on the fiber surface. After alkali solution treatment (Fig. 2 c and d), the material in the interfibrillar region were obviously etched away. Based on the FT-IR results and the structure of natural fibers, the cementing material would be expected to be hemicellulose or lignin. Fig. 2 (b) shows that after 4% alkali treatment that there are still a few impurities that remain on the fiber surface. It indicates that 4% alkali treatment was not good enough to effectively remove the hemicellulose, impurities and bonding material from the flax fiber surface.

Fig. 2 (c and d) shows SEM micrographs of 6% and 8% alkali treated fibers. It can be seen that the surface of the fibers were very clean and rough because of the

removal of the cementing materials (i.e., lignin and hemicellulose) [20, 21]. These results show that with increasing alkali concentration for a 1 hour treatment time, more hemicellulose and lignin was removed. After removal of hemicellulose, the interaction between the fibers is reduced, which made the fibers easier to separate. The SEM images further support the FT-IR results to verify the removal of hemicellulose and lignin. Consequently, the effective fiber surface area available for bonding with the matrix would be increased.

Figure 2. Surface morphology of the untreated and alkali treated kenaf fibers; a) Untreated, b) 4% alkali treatment, c) 6% alkali treatment and d) 8% alkali treatment

Mechanical properties

Fig. 3 (A) shows the tensile properties of alkali treated and untreated woven flax fiber composites with various concentrations of alkali treatment. It can be seen that the tensile strength significantly increased with increasing alkali concentration, 9.186 MPa for 4%, 10.736 MPa for 6% and 13.046 MPa for 8% alkali treated composites. The enhancement in tensile strength in the alkali treated fiber composites is attributed to the improved wetting of the alkali treated fiber with the matrix [22]. Indeed, by removal of impurities and waxy substances from the fiber surface and the creation of a rougher after alkalisiation, the mechanical interlocking and thus the interface quality is improved [23]. Fig.3 (A) shows that the maximum tensile modulus was 1.981 GPa at 4% alkali treatment. However, the modulus of 6% and 8% alkali treated composites were lower than that of the untreated and 4% alkali treated composites. The improved tensile modulus of the 4% alkali treated composite could be due to the removal of lignin and hemicelluloses from the fibers thus causing fiber fibrillation, which increased the area available for contact with the matrix. Hence, the resin was able to penetrate much better through the fiber's surface and this improved the fiber-matrix interaction at the composite's interface.

Fig. 3 (B) shows the flexural properties of surface-treated flax fiber composites reasonable increases compared to the untreated fiber composites. In the case of the 4% alkali treated composite, the flexural modulus was around 647 MPa 649 MPa for 6% and 719 MPa for 8% alkali treated composites. When flax fibers are treated with NaOH the strength of the composites increases compared to that of the untreated flax fibers due to the intrinsically increased strength of the fibers and shows a continuous increasing trend throughout the entire alkali treatment. Fig. 3 (B) shows the flexural strength of the composites with various alkali treatments. It can be seen in Fig. 3 (B) that the flexural strength decreased with increased alkali treatment. The composite with 4% alkali treatment had higher flexural strength compared to the 6% and 8% alkali treatment composites. The flexural strength of the 4% alkali treated composite was 12% higher than that of the 8% alkali treated composite. This reflects the contribution of alkali treatment in terms of changes to fiber properties and enhancement of matrix-fiber adhesion.

Figure 3. Mechanical properties of woven flax fiber/co-polyester biocomposites (A) tensile properties; (B) flexural properties

DMA analysis

Fig. 4 shows the storage modulus and tan delta of alkali treated and untreated woven flax fiber reinforced composites with variation of alkali treatments. The effect of alkali treatment on the storage modulus of the composites can be observed by comparing it to that of the untreated fiber composites. Fig. 4 (A) shows that the storage modulus of the 4 and 6% alkali treated fiber composites are higher than that of the untreated fiber composite, due to the alkali treatment effect imparted by the flax fibers [24, 25]. The storage modulus increased by 44% and 31% in the cases of 4% and 6% alkali treated composites, when compared to untreated fiber composites at -70°C . This suggested that the adhesion between the co-polyester and the treated flax fiber was better. Therefore, the removal of lignin is a key step in producing high modulus composites [19]. Furthermore, the storage modulus of the composites decreased with increased NaOH treatment. It can be seen in Fig. 4 (A) that the 4% alkali treated fiber composite had higher storage modulus than that of the 6 and 8% treated fiber composites. There was a significant fall in the regions between -36°C and -23°C . These DMA results show important variations in the main relaxation temperature,

which can be linked both to interactions resulting in a decrease of chain mobility and to a regular reinforcing effect.

Fig. 4 (B) shows the loss factor of the untreated and treated composites as a function of temperature, where the ratio of storage modulus and loss modulus gives the tangent of the phase angle data, a measure of energy dissipation. The loss factor in the transition region measures the imperfections in the elasticity of a polymer, with the possibility of additional losses occurring at the matrix-fiber interface [26, 27]. From Fig. 4 (B) it can be seen that the treated fibre composites' (except for the 8% alkali treatment) contribution to the damping is extremely low compared to that of the untreated fiber composite. This suggested that the combined attenuation of treated fiber reinforced composites would be mainly caused by the molecular motion of the matrix and the interaction at the fiber/matrix interface. Moreover, the removal of the lignin in treated fibers leads to a change in the extent of hydrogen-bonding, affecting the tan delta of the composites.

Fig.4 The DMA analysis of woven flax fiber and co-polyester green composites; (A) storage modulus and (B) tan delta

Fracture analysis of biocomposites

Fig. 5 (a) shows the SEM micrograph of the untreated woven flax fibre/co-polyester composite fractured surface. The average value of the tensile strength for this composite is 6.733 MPa. From this figure it is seen clearly that a big gap has occurred between the fiber and matrix, which could either occur because of poor approximation during composite manufacture. The result is in agreement with the work of Suriani et al. [28]. It can be seen that the surface of the fiber is clean. This suggests a poor adhesion between the fiber and matrix. A SEM micrograph of a fractured sample of the 8% alkali treated flax fiber reinforced co-polyester composite is shown in Fig. 3(b). The average tensile strength for this sample is 13.045 MPa, which is 48.55% higher than for the untreated fiber composite. The figure shows a significantly good bonding between fibre and matrix. It may be that the fiber surface is rougher than in the untreated fiber composites and this contributes to the enhancement of the bonding strength between fiber and matrix. Better adhesion was observed for the higher alkali concentrations, but the 6% and 8% alkali treated composites does not show better

tensile modulus compared to the 4% alkali treated composite, due to the damage or loss of stiffness of the fibers.

Figure 3. The fracture surface morphology of untreated and alkali treated woven flax fiber biocomposites

Conclusions

The surface and thermal properties of untreated and alkali treated woven flax fibers have been studied. The FT-IR analyses showed that the alkali treated flax fiber does not show a hemicellulose peak at 1735 cm^{-1} compared to untreated fiber. This indicates that the hemicellulose was removed from the fiber surface. The morphological changes were examined using electron microscopy. It has been shown that 4% alkali treatment was ineffective to remove the impurities on the fiber surface. However, 6% and 8% alkali treated fibers showed the cleanest and rougher surface than that of the untreated fiber. The 4% and 6% alkali treated fibers showed higher thermal stability compared to the untreated and 8% alkali treated fibers. The tensile strength and flexural modulus of the alkali treated composites increased with increased alkali treatment concentration and this could be due to a reduction in the hydrophilic nature of flax fiber as a result of the alkali treatment, which therefore increased the interfacial bonding between fiber and matrix.

The dynamic mechanical properties (storage modulus and tan delta) of untreated and alkali treated flax fiber composites have been studied from -75 to $150\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. In all cases the storage modulus decreased upon increasing the temperature due to increased segmental mobility. The glass transition temperatures of the 4 and 6% alkali treated composites was found to be shifted to higher temperatures compared to the untreated composites and can be explained based on improved fiber-matrix adhesion. The SEM results showed that the bonding between fiber and matrix improved after alkali treatment.

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